

An electronic arrangement of the periodic table for assigning ideal electronic configuration of the elements

Narendra Singh Bhandari* and Girish Chandra Shah

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University, Soban Singh Jeena Campus, Almora-263 601, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : shah_gc@rediff.co

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Abstract : Systematic organization of the elements and emergence of the periodic table is one of the most important events in the history of chemical education. This systematization is a virtual grouping of elements in respect to the periodicity in their properties. This periodicity occurs because of the resemblance in electronic structure of the elements. So electron configuration of elements is of prime importance to know about the periodicity in chemical as well as physical nature of the elements. To find out ideal electronic configuration, an energy level diagram that consists of the order of filling of atomic orbital is generally used. Here a periodic table, derived from the real order of increasing energy of atomic orbital for the electron filling, is presented. In it, elements appear in their natural order of atomic numbers, so from this table one can easily find out the valence as well as complete electronic configuration of any arbitrarily chosen element from atomic number 1 to 170.

Keywords : Periodic table, electronic configuration, electronic arrangement.

Elements exhibit periodicity in their physical and chemical properties and it is this periodicity that has been used to develop some fourteen categories of more than seven hundred forms of periodic charts of the elements upto 1974¹ and thereafter around million numbers upto date (Internet version). Almost all the charts are periodicity based groupings to study the physical and chemical properties of the elements. There are only few periodic tables²⁻⁴ that are mainly used to find out ideal electronic structure of the elements. Attempted here is an electronic periodic table, a valence electron based groupings of the elements, which can be used to determine the ideal electronic configuration of the elements, in particular.

The format :

A mnemonic that in its different forms appears in most of the graduate level inorganic textbooks^{4,5} to remember the order in which electrons fill the orbitals, is given in Fig. 1(A). These orbitals, in their real order of increasing energy, are arranged as they actually appear in the atoms in two columns and given in Fig. 1(B). These two columns i.e. A and B of atomic orbital along with total valence electrons of the elements with atomic number 1 to 170 are used to construct the electronic periodic table as is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. (A) Occupancy order of atomic orbitals and (B) real order of increasing energy for the electron filling of atomic orbitals which is used to build up periodic chart of the elements.

In this table there are in all twenty vertical columns named as groups and are numbered as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.... 19, 20. The orbital columns X and Y are inserted before

Note

		GROUP																				
		COLUMN																				
ORBITAL	A	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	
1s	H ¹	He ²																				
2s	Li ³	Be ⁴	B ⁵	C ⁶	N ⁷	O ⁸	F ⁹	Ne ¹⁰														
3s	Na ¹¹	Mg ¹²	Al ¹³	Si ¹⁴	P ¹⁵	S ¹⁶	Cl ¹⁷	Ar ¹⁸														
4s	K ¹⁹	Ca ²⁰	Sc ²¹	Ti ²²	V ²³	Cr ²⁴	Mn ²⁵	Fe ²⁶	Co ²⁷	Ni ²⁸	Cu ²⁹	Zn ³⁰										
5s	Rb ³⁷	Sr ³⁸	Y ³⁹	Zr ⁴⁰	Nb ⁴¹	Mo ⁴²	Tc ⁴³	Ru ⁴⁴	Rh ⁴⁵	Pd ⁴⁶	Ag ⁴⁷	Cd ⁴⁸										
6s	Cs ⁵⁵	Ba ⁵⁶	La ⁵⁷	Ce ⁵⁸	Pr ⁵⁹	Nd ⁶⁰	Pm ⁶¹	Sm ⁶²	Eu ⁶³	Gd ⁶⁴	Tb ⁶⁵	Dy ⁶⁶	Ho ⁶⁷	Er ⁶⁸	Tm ⁶⁹	Yb ⁷⁰						
7s	Fr ⁸⁷	Ra ⁸⁸	Ac ⁸⁹	Th ⁹⁰	Pa ⁹¹	U ⁹²	Np ⁹³	Pu ⁹⁴	Am ⁹⁵	Cm ⁹⁶	Bk ⁹⁷	Cf ⁹⁸	Es ⁹⁹	Fm ¹⁰⁰	Md ¹⁰¹	No ¹⁰²						
8s	Uue ¹¹⁹	Uuh ¹²⁰	Uuq ¹¹³	Rf ¹⁰⁴	Db ¹⁰⁵	Sg ¹⁰⁶	Bh ¹⁰⁷	Hs ¹⁰⁸	Mt ¹⁰⁹	Ds ¹¹⁰	Rg ¹¹¹	Uub ¹¹²										
9s			Uuq ¹¹⁴	Uup ¹¹⁵	Uuh ¹¹⁶	Uus ¹¹⁷	Uuo ¹¹⁸															
			121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138		
			139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152						
			153	154	155	156	157	158	159	160	161	162										
			163	164	165	166	167	168														
			169	170																		

Fig. 2. Electronic periodic table for ideal electronic configuration of the elements.

group 1 and 3 respectively. This insertion of orbital columns divides the periodic chart in to two distinct regions. The group 1 and 2 comprise *s*-elements only. The *p*, *d*, *f* and *g* elements find place in main block of the table extending from groups 3 to 20. For *s* groups 1 and 2, the valence electron numbers are 1 and 2 respectively. Group number minus 2 is the valence electron number of the elements extending from group 3 to 20.

The horizontal rows represent the periods of the elements. The principal quantum number of *s* orbital (column X) is the period number and is not given separately in the present scheme. The periods 1, 2 and 3 are similar to planar block format of the periodic table⁶. In 4th and 5th periods the *p*-series of elements in order of their valence electrons are placed below the *d*-series elements in a separate row. Similar trend is followed for periods 6 and 7 in which *d*- and *p*-series elements are placed below the *f*-elements. In 8th period, *g*-elements are followed by *f*, *d* and *p* series elements respectively in order of their energy profile. Each period, except period 1, starts with *s*-orbital and ends with *p*-orbital. Only two theoretical elements 169 and 170 are shown in the 9th period. Thus in all there are eighteen horizontal rows in the present scheme of arrangement of the elements (Fig. 2). The elements with irregular electronic configuration are shown in shades.

How to use the electronic periodic table :

To illustrate the use of the electronic periodic scheme, let us determine the electronic configuration of the elements whose atomic numbers are 38, 76 and 130.

The element with atomic number 38 is strontium, which is located in period 5 and in column number 2. Therefore, the valence electron configuration is $5s^2$. Now writing the atomic orbitals of both the columns with their electron capacity up to $5s$ as shown in Fig. 3 gives complete electronic configuration of Sr and is $1s^2, 2s^2 2p^6, 3s^2 3p^6, 4s^2 3d^{10} 4p^6, 5s^2$ or [Kr] $5s^2$.

1s	2		
2s	2	2p	6
3s	2	3p	6
4s	2	3d	10
		4p	6
5s	2		

Sr = 38

Fig. 3. Location of Sr in the electronic periodic table.

Osmium is the element of atomic number 76. It is located in $5d$ series of 6th period and in group 8 of the table (Fig. 4). So the valence electrons in $5d$ orbital are $8-2=6$ i.e. $5d^6$. The outer shell electron configuration is $6s^2 4f^{14} 5d^6$ and valence electron configuration is $6s^2 5d^6$. The complete electron configuration of the element is [Xe] $6s^2 4f^{14} 5d^6$ or $1s^2, 2s^2 2p^6, 3s^2 3p^6, 4s^2 3d^{10} 4p^6, 5s^2 4d^{10} 5p^6, 6s^2 4f^{14} 5d^6$.

1s	2		
2s	2	2p	6
3s	2	3p	6
4s	2	3d	10
		4p	6
5s	2	4d	10
		5p	6
6s	2	4f	14
		5d	10
		6p	6

Os = 76

Fig. 4. Location of Os in the electronic periodic table.

Element (Utn) with atomic number 130 is located in 8th period and in $5g$ series. Its group number is 12 so the number of valence electron is $12-2=10$ and *g*-orbital electron configuration will be $5g^{10}$. The outer shell electron configuration is $8s^2 5g^{10}$ and is also the valence electron configuration of the element. The complete electron configuration is [Uuo] $8s^2 5g^{10}$ or $1s^2, 2s^2 2p^6, 3s^2 3p^6, 4s^2 3d^{10} 4p^6, 5s^2 4d^{10} 5p^6, 6s^2 4f^{14} 6d^{10} 6p^6, 7s^2 5f^{14} 6d^{10} 7p^6, 8s^2 5g^{10}$ (Fig. 5).

1s	2		
2s	2	2p	6
3s	2	3p	6
4s	2	3d	10
		4p	6
5s	2	4d	10
		5p	6
6s	2	4f	14
		5d	10
		6p	6
7s	2	5f	14
		6d	10
		7p	6
8s	2	5g	10

Utn = 130

Fig. 5. Location of Utn in the electronic periodic table.

Note

In known elements, there are 18 elements that exhibit irregularities in valence shell electron configuration and are shown in Table 1 with their idealized electron

configuration for the purpose of comparison. This can help users to get complete information about the electronic structure of the known elements.

Table 1. Elements that exhibit irregularities in ground state electronic configuration

Element	Idealized configuration	Observed configuration
Cr (24)	[Ar] $3d^4 4s^2$	[Ar] $3d^5 4s^1$
Cu (29)	[Ar] $3d^9 4s^2$	[Ar] $3d^{10} 4s^1$
Nb (41)	[Kr] $4d^3 5s^2$	[Kr] $4d^4 5s^1$
Mo (42)	[Kr] $4d^4 5s^2$	[Kr] $3d^5 5s^1$
Ru (44)	[Kr] $4d^6 5s^2$	[Kr] $4d^7 5s^1$
Rh (45)	[Kr] $4d^7 5s^2$	[Kr] $4d^8 5s^1$
Pd (46)	[Kr] $4d^8 5s^2$	[Kr] $4d^{10} 5s^0$
Ag (47)	[Kr] $4d^9 5s^2$	[Kr] $4d^{10} 5s^1$
La (57)	[Xe] $4f^1 5d^0 5s^2$	[Xe] $4f^0 5d^1 5s^2$
Gd (64)	[Xe] $4f^8 5d^0 6s^2$	[Xe] $4f^7 5d^1 6s^2$
Pt (78)	[Xe] $4f^14 5d^8 6s^2$	[Xe] $4f^14 5d^9 6s^1$
Au (79)	[Xe] $4f^14 5d^9 6s^2$	[Xe] $4f^14 5d^{10} 6s^1$
Ac (89)	[Rn] $5f^1 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^0 6d^1 7s^2$
Th (90)	[Rn] $5f^2 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^0 6d^2 7s^2$
Pa (91)	[Rn] $5f^3 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^2 6d^1 7s^2$
U (92)	[Rn] $5f^4 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^3 6d^1 7s^2$
Np (93)	[Rn] $5f^5 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^4 6d^1 7s^2$
Cm (96)	[Rn] $5f^8 6d^0 7s^2$	[Rn] $5f^7 6d^1 7s^2$

Conclusion :

Elements, in the present scheme of periodic arrangement, are grouped according to total number of valence electrons they have in their idealized electronic configuration. So this scheme if used as a chart during periodic discussion on electronic configuration would make it interesting and tangible for the students.

References

1. E. G. Mazurs, "Graphic Representation of the Periodic Table during One Hundred Years", University of Alabama, Alabama, 1974.
2. R. I. Rich, *Chem. Educ.*, 2005, **82**, 1761.
3. H. von M. Osorio and A. Goldschmidt, *Chem. Educ.*, 1989, **66**, 758.
4. H. von M. Osorio, *Chem. Educ.*, 1990, **67**, 563.
5. J. Huheey, "Inorganic Chemistry", 2nd ed., Harper & Row, New York, 1978, 27.
6. G. T. Seaborg, *Chem. Educ.*, 1969, **46**, 626.